

MEDICAL TOURISM - BUSINESS ON TRAVEL WITH HEALTH BENEFITS

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Abstract. One of the promising and fast-growing sectors of the tourism business is medical tourism - travel for the purpose of improving health and receiving medical services outside the region of permanent residence. In leading countries, this area has been developing successfully for a long time. Sanatoriums and clinics in [Switzerland](#), [Germany](#), and [Italy](#) accepted wealthy patients from all over [Europe](#) back in the 18th century. And in recent years, along with traditional areas of health recreation and spa treatment, the popularity and economic importance of the tourism sector associated with receiving high-tech medical services has grown.

Keywords: [medical tourism](#), tourism business, health services, sanatoriums.

Аннотация. Одним из перспективных и быстрорастущих направлений туристического бизнеса является медицинский туризм — путешествия с целью оздоровления и получения медицинских услуг за пределами региона постоянного проживания. В ведущих странах это направление давно и успешно развивается. Санатории и клиники Швейцарии, Германии, Италии принимали состоятельных пациентов со всей Европы еще в XVIII веке. А в последние годы наряду с традиционными направлениями оздоровительного отдыха и санаторно-курортного лечения возросла популярность и экономическая значимость туристической сферы, связанной с получением высокотехнологичных медицинских услуг.

Ключевые слова: медицинский туризм, туристический бизнес, оздоровительные услуги, санатории.

Annotatsiya. Turizm biznesining istiqbolli va tez rivojlanayotgan sohalaridan biri bu tibbiy turizm - doimiy yashash joyidan tashqarida sog'liqni saqlash va tibbiy xizmatlarni olish maqsadida sayohat qilishdir. Etakchi mamlakatlarda bu soha uzoq vaqtdan beri muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanib kelmoqda. Shveytsariya, Germaniya va Italiyadagi sanatoriylar va klinikalar 18-asrda butun Evropadan badavlat bemorlarni qabul qilgan. So‘nggi yillarda an‘anaviy sog‘lomlashtirish va kurortda davolanish yo‘nalishlari bilan bir qatorda yuqori texnologiyali tibbiy xizmatlarni olish bilan bog‘liq turizm sohasining ham mashhurligi va iqtisodiy ahamiyati ortib bormoqda.

Kalit so‘zlar: tibbiy turizm, turizm biznesi, sog'liqni saqlash xizmatlari, sanatoriylar.

Medical tourism is gaining more and more popularity today. Millions of people travel to other countries every year to undergo treatment there and combine rest with receiving highly qualified medical care. To raise this sphere to a new level, our country has all the necessary conditions: picturesque nature, mild climate, plenty of sun, and also an important factor - affordable prices. The concept of development of the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2025, approved by the Decree of the Head of State "On comprehensive measures to radically improve the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated December 7, 2018, provides for the enhanced development of medical tourism in the country. The medical tourism market is considered one of the most dynamic sectors of the economy today. This tourism sector will grow by an average of 9.9% per year. It is no coincidence that today more than 50 countries declare the development of medical tourism at the level of state policy. This is a direction of tourism that provides for the targeted organization of treatment of citizens abroad, the

creation of opportunities and methods for obtaining the necessary medical services outside the country of residence, with the simultaneous provision of tourist and additional services. Its goal is the broad development of the healthcare sector in the country, among the important tasks are improving the quality of specialized services at the level of international standards, the introduction of modern technologies and equipment in the field, improving the qualifications of medical personnel, developing medical tourism packages, and developing related industries (tourism, logistics, culture, catering). It is customary to distinguish between medical and health tourism. The former involves receiving high-tech medical care (in a hospital or medical center), the latter - general health improvement in a resort area. Many countries that are active in the medical tourism market are trying to develop both areas comprehensively, opening new high-tech clinics near resort areas or on their territory. One of the main reasons for the active development of medical tourism is the significant difference in the level of health care and the cost of treatment in different countries. Thus, patients who are unable to receive a certain procedure or service in their home country or do not want to waste time waiting for it, often find similar services abroad, often at a lower price and without delay.

It is no coincidence that the main suppliers of clients for the medical tourism industry are [Europe](#) and North [America](#), where the high level of development of medical technologies is combined with no less high cost of medical services. Consumers from five countries - [the USA](#), [Germany](#), [Japan](#), [France](#) and [Austria](#) - provided 63% of the world demand for foreign medical services. According to the results of a survey of medical tourism consumers from several countries (average figures) indicate that the main motives of medical tourism consumers are the need to receive high-tech assistance (42% of respondents), the search for higher quality medical services (33%), the need for urgent assistance (15%) and the desire to save on treatment. And the most popular services are weight loss (32%), orthopedics (22%), cosmetology (12%) and spinal diseases (2%).

The list of the most active host countries is constantly expanding as national healthcare develops and programs are implemented to stimulate the development of medical tourism. The top ten leading countries were India, Hungary, [Mexico](#), [Singapore](#), [Thailand](#), Barbados, [Brazil](#), [Israel](#), South Korea, and [Turkey](#). India alone provided medical services to foreign tourists worth approximately \$2.3 billion. In all of the above-mentioned countries, the cost of medical services is much lower than in the United States and leading European countries, and the number of clinics certified by the *Joint Commission International (JCI) system* is constantly growing (usually with government support).

Regardless of the degree of commercialization of the medical sector in different countries, the determining role in the development of medical tourism as an industry belongs to the state. It influences not only the level of national high-tech medicine (directly - through the development of state clinics, or indirectly - through stimulation and support of the development of private medical centers), but also forms special legislation, is engaged in the formation of a common host infrastructure (roads, hotels, customs, etc.), without which the systemic development of host medical tourism is impossible.

For example, such a program, being developed in South Korea, provides for the simplification of entry rules into the country for “medical tours,” stimulation of investments in medical companies, improvement of transportation and accommodation conditions, training of specialists in the field of management and promotion of medical services abroad, etc. The state even assumes insurance risks for medical care for foreigners.

The Tourism Authority of Thailand has developed a program to promote medical tourism specifically for citizens of the CIS countries, focusing on full diagnostics in clinics with Russian-speaking staff at prices “like for our own.” Thus, according to *Medical & Health Tourism Magazine*, today some Thai clinics serve exclusively foreign patients, in others the share of foreigners is 30-50%. [Israel](#), Korea, Turkey, Thailand, [China](#) and other countries are actively promoting the services of their high-tech clinics in foreign markets, intending to turn medical tourism into a significant sector of the national economy.

In Uzbekistan, despite the presence of high-tech medical centers, including world-class ones, only the beginnings of medical tourism are emerging. This direction is developing spontaneously, and all success stories happen not so much thanks to, but in spite of the state policy in the field of health care and tourism, which, by the way, are under the jurisdiction of different ministries. The pioneers of host medical tourism in Uzbekistan were private dental clinics, providing services to former compatriots who went abroad.

It cannot be said that outbound medical tourism in Uzbekistan is very popular, since the cost of a health tour is on average 1.3 times higher than a regular trip, and high-tech assistance abroad can be several times more expensive.

The increase in the cost of medical care in some countries of the world compared to Uzbekistan, if so, according to the Association of Tour Operators of Uzbekistan, the share of "medical tours" in the total number of sold foreign tours from year to year does not exceed 1-1.5%. The most popular are health resort vacations, some types of high-tech care and the so-called check-up. As we can see, "health" and "medical" tourism are not always distinguished by experts when assessing the market.

Most medical tourists from Uzbekistan traditionally go to India (45%) and Germany (20%). Naturally, there is no talk of saving money. However, in recent years, there has been a growth in popularity of other destinations: Turkey, [Singapore](#), Switzerland, France and Eastern European countries. The most popular procedures are in such areas as cardiac surgery, transplantology, eye surgery, oncology, as well as treatment of chronic diseases, which requires modern technologies and specialized postoperative care.

The presence in our country of a network of well-equipped clinics and medical centers could become the basis for the development of a full-fledged medical tourism sector, even if at first it is domestic or focused on neighboring countries. True, this will require certain changes in the principles of organizing the work of medical institutions, but with a great desire it is possible to do without even radical reforms, within the framework of existing legislation and using public-private partnership.

In our country, it is impossible to fully implement such an approach not only because the system of budget-insurance medicine adopted in Uzbekistan assumes the assignment of patients to certain medical institutions. Our medical institutions are mostly focused on a certain segment of the treatment process - diagnostics, conservative or surgical treatment, rehabilitation or restorative treatment. And the division of medical institutions into regional, departmental, private - with different principles and sources of financing, different organizational approaches to management, patient management, dispatching, etc.

The development of infrastructure for receiving and servicing visiting patients and their accompanying persons requires special measures. For example, there are very few hotels capable of accepting wheelchair users even in Tashkent, not to mention the regions. Highly qualified specialists, to whom patients would want to come from other regions and countries, are few and far between, even in large cities. And, as a rule, they are all very busy, combining work in state

clinics, where they gain the necessary experience and improve their qualifications, with incomparably better-paid work in private medical centers, the prices of which are unaffordable for most patients. Therefore, it is quite difficult to maintain professional tone at the proper level. And the services of clinics and doctors of the "average" level are capable of attracting " medical tourists " only from other countries of Central [Asia](#) .

Another most probable direction of development of medical, or rather, health tourism in Uzbekistan is sanatorium and resort treatment. A full-fledged industry with unified management and regulation, with its own scientific base, personnel training system, etc.

It is obvious that the efforts of all parties interested in the development of this direction should be aimed at providing truly effective health recreation programs for reasonable prices. This is the only way to support the forced (for now) demand and attract clients in the future.

Here, according to representatives of the tourism business, a lot depends on the system of distributing vouchers, since there are quite a lot of treatment factors, as well as diseases that they affect, and it is difficult for non-specialists to understand them. Today, according to the Association of Tour Operators of Uzbekistan, only 8-9% of clients choose a sanatorium on the recommendation of a doctor. Meanwhile, since we are talking about health improvement, the role of doctors in choosing a sanatorium should be more significant. *"Only a doctor can recommend a particular resort in accordance with medical indications . "*

In general, the processes occurring today in the health resort industry represent a continuing transition from free subsidized medicine to medicine operating on a commercial basis. The development of health resort organizations is unsystematic, with the main criterion and guiding vector being, as a rule, the interests and capabilities of the owners.

However, doctors do not know how to implement a comprehensive approach to the organizational and methodological support and management of this industry in the new economic conditions or at least systematize the existing problems - financing, education and advanced training of specialists, purchase of new equipment, etc. Even new criteria for distinguishing sanatorium institutions from spas and other recreational organizations are still being developed. Medical tourism in Uzbekistan is a young and successfully developing area of local tourism. Today, Tashkent has many modern private clinics and medical centers offering inpatient and outpatient services, surgical treatment and dental care at very competitive prices, and most of these clinics also accept international insurance. Modern medical centers in Tashkent are equipped with high-quality equipment, qualified specialists work here, including foreign ones. Treatment in Uzbekistan will be a convenient option for foreigners traveling in Central Asia or temporarily residing in its territory. High-quality inexpensive laboratory tests, diagnostic tests and basic medical procedures can be easily included in your travel schedule. Those who prefer alternative treatments will appreciate the qualified specialists of Uzbekistan who offer acupuncture, homeopathic treatment and massage therapy.

Medical tourism in Uzbekistan is especially popular in the field of dentistry. Here, teeth are treated and prosthetically treated at a high level; the list of services provided by medical institutions includes all the main modern dental procedures, including the installation of high-quality fillings, enamel restoration of varying degrees, the installation of crowns, veneers , dentures and much more. There are many dental clinics in Tashkent equipped with the latest equipment. They employ highly qualified dentists, general practitioners, surgeons, orthopedists, periodontists , implantologists , orthodontists with good training, many of whom have internship experience in large international clinics. There is also a regular exchange of experience with leading foreign medical institutions .

It was in Uzbekistan, near the city of Bukhara, that the brilliant physician Avicenna was born, whose name is known and revered throughout the world. The works he wrote laid the fundamental foundation for the study of medicine and medicines. Avicenna's work lives on in Uzbekistan to this day: specialists use the knowledge passed down by healers from generation to generation, improving it. The most popular procedures of traditional medicine in Uzbekistan are acupuncture, hirudotherapy, mud therapy, water procedures, spa, climatotherapy. Among the centers and clinics providing such procedures are: [Hayat](#), Orzu, Shox Med and others. And also medical tourism in Uzbekistan is actively developing the direction of cosmetology and surgery. In Uzbekistan, you can carry out a fairly wide range of procedures in plastic and aesthetic surgery: blepharoplasty, facial plastic surgery, otoplasty, rhinoplasty, abdominoplasty, mammoplasty, liposuction, intimate plastic surgery. Tashkent clinics have the most modern equipment, prices, compared to neighboring countries, are lower. In the capital, such clinics as Estimed, KASMED, Gatling are available Med, Medas and others.

Medical tourism in our country is just beginning to emerge as a target direction and component of state policy. Citizens of neighboring countries have always come to Uzbekistan clinics for treatment and consultation. However, they arrived independently, directly to the institutions, without contacting specialized travel agencies and specially created departments for the development of medical tourism. The high quality of services provided and affordable prices for them have attracted and will continue to attract foreign citizens to Uzbekistan, so medical tourism has great prospects here. You can also improve your health by choosing a vacation in one of the sanatoriums of Uzbekistan.

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